

Contribution to the Bulgarian fauna of Heteroptera

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Abstract. Among the announced 16 Heteroptera species 7 are new for the Bulgarian fauna. The presence of another three species on the territory of the country is confirmed. New localities for 6 species collected until now only from single ones are represented as well. The discovery of *Phytocoris minor* and *Atractotomus marcoi* on *Pinus nigra* is the first data about the biology of these dendrobiont species in Bulgaria.

Key words: Faunistics, Heteroptera, Bulgaria

Introduction

The following Heteroptera species are subjects of this work: new ones for the Bulgarian fauna (in the text they are marked with *) or species announced until now only from a single locality in Bulgaria or the data on their presence need confirmation.

The position of the localities is given in UTM code (UTM Zones 34, 35). The feeding plant or the habitat, where the insect was collected, is represented as well if there are enough data available. The method of collection is mentioned only if it differs from mowing with an entomological net or beating the tree branches with a net for dendrobiont species. The material is deposited in the authors' collections in the National Museum of Natural History and in the Institute of Zoology.

Species account

CERATOCOMBIDAE

Ceratombus (s. str.) *coleopratus* (Zetterstedt, 1819)

Material examined: Bulgaria NG 45, Strandzha Mts. 80 m alt., near Veleka River, Kachul Site, wet meadow, pitfall traps, 01.10-16.11.2000, 3 ♂♂, leg. N. Kodzhabashev & M. Langourov; Bulgaria GL 09, Southern Pirin Mt., 450 m alt., SE slope of Sveti Iliya Hill, near v. Kalimantsi, communities of *Quercus coccifera*, pitfall traps, 01.06-22.06.2002, 1 ♀, leg. M. Langourov.

Notes: Until now this species has been announced for Bulgaria without any data on its locality (STICHEL, 1960). This West Euro-Siberian one is found on the Balkan Peninsula in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece and Macedonia as well (KERZHNER, 1995).

CORIXIDAE

*** *Micronecta (s. str.) carpatica* Wróblewski, 1958**

Material examined: Bulgaria LF 78, Eastern Rhodopes Mts. 450m alt., v. Ribino, a Karst spring in Talashman Dere Protected Site, 18.06.2000, 17 ♂♂ & ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Notes: An European species. For the territory of the Balkan Peninsula it is known from Greece as well (POLHEMUS et al., 1995).

***Micronecta (s. str.) poweri poweri* (Douglas et Scott, 1869)**

Material examined: Bulgaria FP 51, Western Balkan Mts. 500 m alt., Prevalaska River near v. Prevala, 18.07.2000, 11 ♂♂, 15 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Note: A West Euro-Siberian species announced for Bulgaria without locality (STICHEL, 1956).

SALDIDAE

***Saldula c-album* (Fieber, 1859)**

Material examined: Bulgaria FN 81, Vitosha Mt. 1900 m alt., Reserve Torfen Rezervat, Gorno Blato Site, 13.07.1984, 2 ♂ & ♀, leg. M. Josifov.

Note: A Boreo-Montane species announced for Bulgaria without locality (STICHEL, 1960).

*** *Salda muelleri* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Material examined: Bulgaria FN 91, Vitosha Mt. 1800 m alt., near the Fizkulturnik hut, 13.07.1984, 5 ♂♂ & ♀♀, leg. M. Josifov.

Note: A Boreo-Montane species announced for Bulgaria on the basis of an incorrectly determined material from Rila Mt. (JOAKIMOV, 1922).

MICROPHYSIDAE

*** *Myrmedobia jakovlevi* Péricart, 1969**

Material examined: Bulgaria FM 71, Strouma River Valley, 170-240 m alt., 2 km SE of v. Kamenitsa, communities of *Quercus coccifera*, pitfall traps, 27.09-02.11.2002, 1 ♀, leg. M. Langourov.

Notes: The species is new for the fauna of the Balkan Peninsula. Up to now it has been known from Crimea and Georgia (PÉRICART, 1972, 1996a). Probably the species is Ponto-Mediterranean.

*** *Myrmedobia exilis* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: Bulgaria FN 81, Vitosha Mt. 1800 m alt., Platoto, on *Picea abies*, 08.08.1999, 1 ♀, leg. N. Simov.

Notes: An Euro-Siberian species. Until now it has been announced for the territory of the Balkan Peninsula from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia (PÉRICART, 1972, 1996a).

MIRIDAE

Phytocoris (Exophytocoris) minor Kirschbaum, 1856

Material examined: Bulgaria GM 03, Pirin Mt. 1160 m alt., Chalin Valog Site, on *Pinus nigra*, 10.08.2002, 6 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov; Bulgaria GM 03, Pirin Mt. 1040 m, Ravno Bore Site, on *Pinus nigra*, 23.08.2002, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Notes: For the first time in Bulgaria this species was collected in Kresna Gorge on UV light (JOSIFOV, 1986b). Its discovery on *Pinus nigra* is the first data about the biology of this North-Mediterranean species in the country.

Brachycoleus steini Reuter, 1877

Material examined: Bulgaria NG 75, Black Sea Coast, v. Sinemoretz, near the outflow of Veleka River, 22.06.1991, 2 ♂ & ♀, leg. M. Josifov.

Notes: The announcements for Bulgaria of this Ponto-Mediterranean species are from Sliven (HORVÁTH, 1890) and from Slavyanka Mt. (DRENOWSKI, 1937), but the material is lost and the determination is doubtful.

* *Pinalitus viscicola* (Puton, 1888)

Material examined: Bulgaria NG 58, Black Sea Coast, 7 km N of Primorsko, Arkutino Protected Site, on *Viscum album* on *Acer* sp., 12.09.2002, 29 ♂♂, 21 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Note: A West-Palaeartic species known for the Balkan Peninsula from Macedonia, Slovenia and Croatia (KERZHNER & JOSIFOV, 1999).

Cremnocephalus albolineatus Reuter, 1875

Material examined: Bulgaria FM 82, Kresna Gorge 450 m alt., v. Stara Kresna, Hladkata Banya thermal spring, on *Pinus nigra*, 27.05.2001, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Notes: The species is announced for Bulgaria from the Rhodopes Mts. on *Pinus sylvestris* (JOSIFOV, 1980). Its relation to the genus *Pinus*, as well as its discovery at so low altitude on the Mediterranean species *Pinus nigra*, makes us to consider its origin as Mediterranean and the concept of its affiliation to the Boreo-Montane group (JOSIFOV, 1986a; BRÄNDLE & RIEGER, 1999) as incorrect.

Atractotomus marcoi Carapezza, 1982

Material examined: Bulgaria GM 03, Pirin Mt. 1160 m alt., Chalin Valog Site, on *Pinus nigra*, 10.08.2002, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov; Bulgaria KG 21, Western Rhodopes Mts. 1200m alt., Reserve Kastrakli, on *Pinus nigra*, 12.08.2002, 1 ♂, leg. N. Simov; Bulgaria GM 03, Pirin Mt. 1040 m alt., Ravno Bore Site, on *Pinus nigra*, 23.08.2002, 1 ♀, leg. N. Simov.

Notes: For the first time the species is collected in Bulgaria in Kresna Gorge on UV light (JOSIFOV, 1993). It is found on *Pinus laricio* in its locus typicus (CARAPEZZA, 1982). Its discovery on *Pinus nigra* is the first data about the biology of this Ponto-Mediterranean dendrobiont species in Bulgaria.

ANTHOCORIDAE

****Tetraphleps bicuspis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)**

Material examined: Bulgaria FN 82, Vitosha Mt. 1800 m alt., Dolno blato Site near Planinarska pesen hut, on *Larix decidua*, 22.09.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov.

Note: This Boreo-Montane species is known for the Balkan Peninsula also from Slovenia and Croatia (PÉRICART, 1972, 1996b).

***Cardiastethus nazarenus* Reuter, 1884**

Material examined: Bulgaria NG 76, Black Sea Coast, v. Lozenetz, on strobiles of *Cupressus sempervirens*, 06.09.2002, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. N. Simov; Bulgaria NG 58, Black Sea Coast, 7 km N of Primorsko, Arkutino Protected Site, on *Viscum album* on *Acer* sp., 12.09.2002, 2 ♂♂, leg. N. Simov.

Note: A Holomediterranean species collected in Bulgaria on *Tamarix* sp. in Sandanski-Petrich Kettle (GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING & ARNOLD, 1988).

REDUVIIDAE

****Stenolemus novaki* Horváth, 1888**

Material examined: Bulgaria LG 24, Central Rhodopes Mts. 550 m alt., Asenova Krepost Site, 04.06.1989, 1 ♂, leg E. Heiss.

Note: Up to now the species was known for the Balkan Peninsula from only from its terra typica in Dalmatia (PUTSHKOV & PUTSHKOV, 1996).

***Rhynocoris punctiventris* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)**

Material examined: Bulgaria KH 18, Pre-Balkan Area, v. Reselets, 01.07-12.07.1996, 15 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀, leg. M. Josifov.

Note: A Ponto-Mediterranean species. Its locality in Reselets is on the extreme north of its distribution in the Balkan Peninsula (JOSIFOV, 1986a; PROTIC 1998), considerably far from the other known localities in Bulgaria (JOSIFOV, 1964). Apparently the microclimatic conditions in this karst region are favorable for this isolated population.

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Принос към хетероптерната фауна на България (Insecta: Heteroptera)

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(Резюме)

От съобщените 16 вида хетероптери, 7 са нови за българската фауна. Други три вида са потвърдени за страната. За шест вида, известни досега само от едно находище, са посочени нови такива. Дендробионтните хетероптери *Phytocoris minor* и *Atractotomus marcoi* са установени по *Pinus nigra*, което представлява първи опит за изследване на биологията на тези видове в България.